

A RANDOMIZED OPEN-LABELLED COMPARATIVE CLINICAL STUDY TO EVALUATE THE EFFICACY OF *IKSHU PANEeya KSHARA* AND *MULAKA PANEeya KSHARA* IN THE MANAGEMENT OF *MUTRASHMARI* WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO UROLITHIASIS

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ABSTRACT

Sushruta Samhita is one of the foundational texts of *Ayurveda*, composed by *Acharya Sushruta*, who is known as the father of plastic surgery. *Mutrashmari* holds a significant place due to its prevalence, clinical challenges, and potential complications if untreated. *Acharya Sushruta* has classified *Mutrashmari* under *Ashtamahagada* due to its difficult management and life-threatening nature. *Sushruta* also provided both conservative management with *kashayas*, *paneeya kshara* and *yavagu paana* along with dietary measures in *Tarunavastha* and *Shashtra Karma* including *Ashmari bhedana* in *Pravridhavastha* as treatment modalities. The disease *Mutrashmari* can be correlated to Urolithiasis. Prevalence of Urolithiasis is 10-20% in the general population and overall, the incidence of urinary tract stones increases with age, being more common between the ages of 30-50 years. The recurrent nature of Urolithiasis makes it difficult to treat. *Paneeya Kshara* is a conservative therapy for the management of *Mutrashmari* (Urolithiasis) in *Tarunavastha*.

KEYWORDS: *Mutrashmari*; Urolithiasis; *Ikshu paneeya kshara*; *Mulaka paneeya kshara*; *Pashanabhedadi kwatha churna*; *Anupana*; *Paneeya kshara*.

INTRODUCTION

Mutrashmari is a *krichrasadhya vyadhi*^[1], one among the *Ashtamahagada rogas*^[2], *Ashmari* in which *Ashma* means stone and *Ari* means enemy. *Ashmari* which behave like an enemy to the body. Formation of *mutrashmari* is due to drying of *kapha* because of the action of *vata* and *pitta*, presenting with sharp excruciating pain, burning micturition and hematuria that disturbs the normal routine of the individuals.^[3] Urolithiasis is a commonest disease of the urinary system. It is a condition where stones formed in the urinary tract composed of hard deposits of minerals and salts that form in the urinary system. Incidence of formation of stone is 20% across the globe, it affect the kidneys, ureters, bladder, and urethra. Treatment of urolithiasis includes Conservative management, Flush therapy and Surgical management like Extracorporeal Shock Wave Lithotripsy, Ureterscopy these treatments is cost effective along with the complications like infection, left out stone fragments, ureteral injury and

increased recurrence rate. Therefore, there is a need for an effective conservative management approach that is cost-effective, safe, and minimizes recurrence. Drugs that can correct crystalloid and colloid imbalances in urine, prevent supersaturation, and possess antispasmodic, diuretic, and anti-inflammatory properties may play a significant role in managing urolithiasis. In *Ayurveda* treatment of *mutrashmari* includes *Gritha pana*, *Ksheera*, *Kshara*, *Snehapana* and *Shastrachikitsa*.^[4] *Acharya sushruta* given importance to the *Kshara* among the *Shatras* and *Anushatras* and it has properties like *chedana*, *bhedana*, *lekahana*, and *tridoshaghna*^[5] these properties helps in the disintegration of stone and decreases the recurrence rate. Its *Shodhana* and *Ropana* properties help heal lacerated mucosa caused by sharp-edged stones. The alkaline nature of *Kshara* helps maintain urinary pH and corrects metabolic disturbances, thereby preventing recurrence. This therapy requires no hospitalization, is palatable, low in dosage, simple in administration, and economically

affordable. *Ikshu Kshara*^[6] is an unexplored drug in the management of *Mutrashmari*. In *Raja Nighantu*, *Ikshu* is mentioned among the *Kshara Dashaka* group. It possesses *Madhura Rasa*, *Sheeta Veerya*, *Vataghna*, and *Mutrala* properties, which help alleviate pain, burning micturition, and hematuria. *Mulaka Kshara*^[7] has already been scientifically proven effective in the management of *Mutrashmari*. *Pashanabhedadi Kwatha Churna Kashaya* possesses *Ashmarighna* and *Shoolahara* properties that further aid in the management of *Ashmari*.^[8]

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- To evaluate the efficacy of *Ikshu Paneeya Kshara* in the management of *Mutrashmari* w.s.r to Urolithiasis.
- To evaluate the efficacy of *Mulaka Paneeya Kshara* in the management of *Mutrashmari* w.s.r to Urolithiasis.
- To compare the efficacy of *Ikshu Paneeya Kshara* and *Mulaka Paneeya Kshara* in the management of *Mutrashmari* w.s.r to Urolithiasis.

METHADODOLOGY

Study Design

A randomized open labelled comparative clinical study containing 40 patients who are diagnosed with *Mutrashmari* was included for the study and randomly allotted into 2 groups namely Group A and Group B with 20 patients each.

INTERVENTION IN GROUP A AND GROUP B.

Groups	No.of patients	Intervention	Dosage
Group-A	20	<i>Ikshu Paneeya Kshara</i>	500mg BD
Group-B	20	<i>Mulaka Paneeya Kshara</i>	500mg BD

- *Anupana*: *Pashanabhedadi Kwatha churna kashya* - 20ml bd in both the groups.
- Administration: Before food, twice a day, for a period of 28 days.
- *Pathya* and *Apathya* advised to the patients.
- Follow up study- After completion of full course of treatment the patients will be asked to attend Shalya OPD for follow up once in a month for three consecutive months.

Clinical Source

40 patients diagnosed with *Mutrashmari* has been selected from OPD and IPD of Taranath Government Ayurveda Medical College and Hospital, Ballari.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- Patient with the clinical features of Urolithiasis like pain abdomen, burning micturition and haematuria.
- Patient having age between 20-60years
- Stone size : $\leq 8\text{mm}$
- Renal calculi with Mild Hydronephrosis

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Contraindication of *Paneeya Kshara*^[9]
- Immune compromised patients
- Suffering from moderate, severe hydronephrosis, staghorn calculi, impacted calculi.
- Suffering from other uncontrolled systemic disease.

INVESTIGATIONS

- CBC, ESR, RFT, RBS,
- HIV, HBsAg,
- Urine routine
- Confirmed by USG

Procedure

- Informed and written consent taken.

DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA

Subjective

- Pain abdomen
- Burning micturition
- Frequency of micturition
- Haematuria

Objective

- Size of stones
- Descent of stone

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

Assessment was done before and after treatment as per the parameters.

PAIN	GRADE 0 - No pain(0) GRADE 1 - Mild pain(1-3) GRADE 2 - Moderate pain(4-6) GRADE3 - Severe pain(7-10)
BURNING MICTURITION	GRADE1 - Absent GRADE 2 - Present
FREQUENCY OF MICTURITION	GRADE0 - Micturition 1 to 3 times in a day GRADE 1 - Micturition 4 to 6 times in a day GRADE 2 - Micturition 7 to 9 times in a day GRADE 3 - Micturition more than 9 times in a day
HAEMATURIA	GRADE0 – Absent GRADE1 – Present

DESCENT OF STONE	GRADE0 – Absent GRADE1 – Present
SIZE OF STONE	GRADE 0 - No stone GRADE 1 - 1-3mm GRADE 2 - 3.1- 6mm GRADE 3 - 6.1- 8mm

Comparison of Group A and Group B with overall changes from before and after treatment.

Parameters	Changes from	Group A	Group B
Pain Abdomen	Before-Day 7	21.62	41.03
	Before-Day 14	29.73	74.36
	Before-Day 21	51.35	92.31
	Before-Day 28	86.49	89.74
Frequency of micturition	Before-Day 7	2.44	26.47
	Before-Day 14	29.27	41.18
	Before-Day 21	34.15	50.00
	Before-Day 28	78.05	88.24
Burning micturition	Before-Day 7	35.00	50.00
	Before-Day 14	40.00	55.00
	Before-Day 21	40.00	60.00
	Before-Day 28	40.00	65.00
Haematuria	Before-Day 7	100.00	66.67
	Before-Day 14	100.00	100.00
	Before-Day 21	100.00	100.00
	Before-Day 28	100.00	100.00
Size of stone	Before-After	61.36	70.73
Descent of stone	Before-After	55.00	75.00
Overall		55.80	69.21

TREATMENT IN GROUP A
USG BEFORE TREATMENT IN GROUP A

A Unit of M/s Shivapavathi Medical Services Pvt Ltd.
 (CIN No: U85310KA 2018PTC111868)

Tel. : 08392 294434
 07204860092

NAME: MR S K HUDA	AGE/SEX: 55 Years / MALE	ID: 78526
REFERRED BY: DR. SHIVALINGAPPA J ARAKERI		10/07/2024

Thanks for the referral.

ULTRASOUND - ABDOMEN & PELVIS

Technique: Trans abdominal USG was performed using curvilinear and high frequency linear probes on Phillips Affinity 70 machine.

LIVER – Liver is normal in size 12.1 cm. Shows normal echotexture. No focal lesion noted. Main portal vein and its branches appear normal. There is no intrahepatic biliary dilatation seen. CBD is not dilated.

GALL BLADDER– Is well distended. No obvious calculus / wall thickening / pericholecystic fluid.

PANCREAS –Head and body are normal. Tail is obscured. Main pancreatic duct is of normal caliber. There is no evidence of parenchymal or ductal calcification seen.

SPLEEN – Spleen is normal in size and echotexture. No focal lesion seen. Splenic vein is normal in caliber.

RIGHT KIDNEY– measures 9.8 x 5.3 cm. Normal in size and echotexture. Cortico medullary differentiation is maintained. There is no evidence of mass lesion seen. PCS is normal. Right ureter is not dilated. **5mm non-obstructive calculus is seen in the upper pole calyx.**

LEFT KIDNEY –measures 10.7 x 4.9 cm. Normal in size and echotexture. Cortico medullary differentiation is maintained. There is no evidence of mass lesion / hyperechoic calculus seen. PCS is normal. Left ureter is not dilated.

PARA AORTIC AREA –Is normal. No obvious retroperitoneal lymphadenopathy seen.

BOWELS –No abnormal dilated bowel loop seen. No obvious bowel wall thickening seen. No obvious dilated appendix seen.

URINARY BLADDER –Is distended and lumen is anechoic. No mass or calculus seen. Bilateral VUJ are normal.

PROSTATE– Normal in size 3.1 x 3.7 x 3.5 cm (Vol: 20.8 cc) and echotexture is normal.

IMPRESSION:

- Right renal non-obstructive calculus. No evidence of hydronephrosis.

Dr Sagarika K, MBBS, MD
 Consultant Radiologist

Disclaimer: Although the scan has been performed in accordance with standard guidelines, the USG modality has got its inherent limitations and scan quality depends on the many factors viz. patient body habitus, bowel gasses, patient positions and co-operation from the patient to undergo the procedure. Tiny renal calculi (usually <5mm) which does not cause shadowing might not always be visualised on USG. The conditions like, early pancreatitis, deep seated appendix or focal bowel wall thickenings might not always be visualized on USG. The USG report needs to be considered as an aid to the clinical diagnosis and not the absolute one. It is suggested to perform further investigations as and when deemed necessary for the given clinical condition.

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USG AFTER TREATMENT IN GROUP A

A Unit of M/s Shivapavathi Medical Services Pvt Ltd.
(CIN No.: U85310KA 2018PTC111868)

Tel. : 08392 294434
07204860092

NAME: MR S K HUDA	AGE/SEX: 55 Years / MALE	ID: 80729
REFERRED BY: DR. SHIVALINGAPPA J ARAKERI		16/08/2024

Thanks for the referral.

ULTRASOUND - ABDOMEN & PELVIS

Technique: Trans abdominal USG was performed using curvilinear and high frequency linear probes on *Phillips Affinity 70 machine.*

LIVER – Liver is normal in size 12.1 cm. Shows normal echotexture. No focal lesion noted. Main portal vein and its branches appear normal. There is no intrahepatic biliary dilatation seen. CBD is not dilated.

GALL BLADDER– Is well distended. No obvious calculus / wall thickening / pericholecystic fluid.

PANCREAS –Head and body are normal. Tail is obscured. Main pancreatic duct is of normal caliber. There is no evidence of parenchymal or ductal calcification seen.

SPLEEN – Spleen is normal in size and echotexture. No focal lesion seen. Splenic vein is normal in caliber.

RIGHT KIDNEY– measures 9.8 x 5.3 cm. Normal in size and echotexture. Cortico medullary differentiation is maintained. There is no evidence of mass lesion / hyperechoic calculus seen. PCS is normal. Right ureter is not dilated.

LEFT KIDNEY –measures 10.7 x 4.9 cm. Normal in size and echotexture. Cortico medullary differentiation is maintained. There is no evidence of mass lesion / hyperechoic calculus seen. PCS is normal. Left ureter is not dilated.

PARA AORTIC AREA –Is normal. No obvious retroperitoneal lymphadenopathy seen.

BOWELS –No abnormal dilated bowel loop seen. No obvious bowel wall thickening seen. No obvious dilated appendix seen. **No e/o ascites seen.**

URINARY BLADDER –Is distended and lumen is anechoic. No mass or calculus seen. Bilateral VUJ are normal.

PROSTATE– Normal in size 3.1 x 3.7 x 3.5 cm (Vol: 20.8 cc) and echotexture is normal.

IMPRESSION:

- No significant abnormality detected.

Dr Sagarika K, MBBS, MD
Consultant Radiologist

Disclaimer: Although the scan has been performed in accordance with standard guidelines, the USG modality has got its inherent limitations and scan quality depends on the many factors viz, patient body habitus, bowel gasses, patient positions and co-operation from the patient to undergo the procedure. Tiny renal calculi (usually <5mm) which does not cause shadowing might not always be visualised on USG. The conditions like, early pancreatitis, deep seated appendix or focal bowel wall thickenings might not always be visualized on USG. The USG report needs to be considered as an aid to the clinical diagnosis and not the absolute one. It is suggested to perform further investigations as and when deemed necessary for the given clinical condition.

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TREATMENT IN GROUP B
USG BEFORE TREATMENT IN GROUP B

A Unit of M/s Shivapavathi Medical Services Pvt Ltd.
 (CIN No: UMS310KA 2018PTC111856)

Tel. : 08392 294434
 07204860092

NAME: MRS LAKSHMI DEVI	AGE/SEX: 57 Years / FEMALE	ID: 82349
REFERRED BY: DR. SHIVU ARAKERI		30/11/2024

Thanks for the referral.

ULTRASOUND - ABDOMEN & PELVIS

Indication: Pain abdomen

Technique: Trans abdominal USG was performed using curvilinear and high frequency linear probes on *Phillips Affinity 70 machine.*

LIVER – The liver is enlarged in size and measures 16.9 cm in its long axis. The liver shows bright echotexture. No focal lesion noted. Main portal vein and its branches appear normal. There is no intrahepatic biliary dilatation seen. CBD is not dilated.

GALL BLADDER– Is well distended. No obvious calculus / wall thickening / pericholecystic fluid.

PANCREAS –Head and body are normal. Tail is obscured. Main pancreatic duct is of normal caliber. There is no evidence of parenchymal or ductal calcification seen.

SPLEEN – Spleen is normal in size and echotexture. No focal lesion seen. Splenic vein is normal in caliber.

RIGHT KIDNEY– measures 8.5 x 4.4 cm. Normal in size and echotexture. Corticomedullary differentiation is maintained. There is no evidence of mass lesion / hyperechoic calculus seen. PCS is normal. Right ureter is not dilated.

LEFT KIDNEY –measures 9.4 x 5.0 cm. Normal in size and echotexture. Corticomedullary differentiation is maintained. There is no evidence of mass lesion seen. PCS is normal. Left ureter is not dilated.

6.8mm non obstructive calculus is seen in the lower pole calyx.

PARA AORTIC AREA –Is normal. No obvious retroperitoneal lymphadenopathy seen.

BOWELS –No abnormal dilated bowel loop seen. No obvious bowel wall thickening seen. No obvious thickened appendix seen.

URINARY BLADDER –Is distended and lumen is anechoic. No mass or calculus seen. Bilateral VUJ are normal.

UTERUS & OVARIES–Small and atrophic (post menopausal status). No adnexal mass lesion noted. POD appears unremarkable.

No e/o ascites seen.

IMPRESSION:

- Left renal non obstructive calculus.
- Mild hepatomegaly with grade I fatty infiltration.

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USG AFTER TREATMENT IN GROUP B

A Unit of M/s Shriparvathi Medical Services Pvt Ltd.
 (CIN No.: UMS310KA 2018PTC111868)

Tel. : 08392 294434
 07204860092

NAME: MRS LAKSHMI DEVI	AGE/SEX: 57 Years / FEMALE	ID: 93565
REFERRED BY: DR. SHIVU ARAKERI		04/01/2025

Thanks for the referral.

ULTRASOUND - ABDOMEN & PELVIS

Indication: Pain abdomen

Technique: Trans abdominal USG was performed using curvilinear and high frequency linear probes on *Phillips Affinity 70 machine*.

LIVER – The liver is enlarged in size and measures 16.9 cm in its long axis. The liver shows bright echotexture. No focal lesion noted. Main portal vein and its branches appear normal. There is no intrahepatic biliary dilatation seen. CBD is not dilated.

GALL BLADDER – Is well distended. No obvious calculus / wall thickening / pericholecystic fluid.

PANCREAS – Head and body are normal. Tail is obscured. Main pancreatic duct is of normal caliber. There is no evidence of parenchymal or ductal calcification seen.

SPLEEN – Spleen is normal in size and echotexture. No focal lesion seen. Splenic vein is normal in caliber.

RIGHT KIDNEY – measures 8.5 x 4.4 cm. Normal in size and echotexture. Corticomedullary differentiation is maintained. There is no evidence of mass lesion / hyperechoic calculus seen. PCS is normal. Right ureter is not dilated.

LEFT KIDNEY – measures 9.4 x 5.0 cm. Normal in size and echotexture. Corticomedullary differentiation is maintained. There is no evidence of mass lesion / hyperechoic calculus seen. PCS is normal. Left ureter is not dilated.

PARA AORTIC AREA – Is normal. No obvious retroperitoneal lymphadenopathy seen.

BOWELS – No abnormal dilated bowel loop seen. No obvious bowel wall thickening seen. No obvious thickened appendix seen.

URINARY BLADDER – Is distended and lumen is anechoic. No mass or calculus seen. Bilateral VUJ are normal.

UTERUS & OVARIES – Small and atrophic (post menopausal status). No adnexal mass lesion noted. POD appears unremarkable.

No e/o ascites seen.

IMPRESSION:

- Mild hepatomegaly with grade I fatty infiltration.
- No other significant abnormality detected.

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DISCUSSION

Probable Mode of Action of *Paneeya Kshara* in *Mutrashmari*

Ayurvedic Perspective

Kshara, with its *Chedana*, *Bhedana*, *Lekhana*, and *Tridoshaghna*^[10] properties, acts on compact molecules of the stone, making them fragile and aiding disintegration. Its *Shodhana* and *Ropana* actions help heal lacerations of the urinary mucosa caused by spiky stones. The alkaline nature of the drug helps maintain

urinary pH and correct metabolic disorders responsible for stone formation, thus preventing recurrence.

Ikshu Paneeya Kshara mode of action

- **Inorganic salts:** contribute to *Ksharana* (corrosive), *Lekhana* (scraping), and *Mutrala* (diuretic) actions, aiding in *Ashmari Bhedana* (breaking urinary calculi).
- **Alkalinization of urine:** Rich in potassium carbonate and sodium carbonate, which raise urinary

pH, helping dissolve uric acid and cystine stones and preventing calcium oxalate aggregation.

- **Litholytic action:** Alkaline salts (K_2CO_3 , Na_2CO_3 , $CaCO_3$) chemically react with the stone matrix, weakening and fragmenting it.
- **Diuretic effect:** Promotes urine flow, flushing out crystals, and preventing stone formation and stasis.
- **Anti-inflammatory effect:** Reduces irritation and inflammation of the urinary mucosa.
- **Antimicrobial effect:** Alkaline medium lowers infection risk in the urinary tract.
- **Antioxidant and membrane-stabilizing effect:** Trace elements and polyphenols reduce oxidative stress on renal tissues.

Mulaka Paneeya Kshara

- *Mulaka possesses Katu-Tikta Rasa, Ushna Virya, and Mutrala properties.* It acts as *Kaphahara* and counteracts *Sheeta Guna*, which is considered an *Upadana Karana* for *Ashmari*, thereby reducing *Vedana*.
- *Chakradatta (Ashmari Chikitsa Adhyaya):* Mentions *Mulaka Paneeya Kshara* as *Ashmari Bhedana* and *Mutrala*.
- *Bhaishajya Ratnavali (60/41–44, Ashmari Chikitsa Prakarana):* Recommends *Mulaka Paneeya Kshara* for the dissolution and expulsion of calculi.

Pashanabhedadi Kwatha Churna Kashaya

- *Pashanabhedadi Kwatha Churna Kashaya* has *Ashmarighna* and *Shoolahara* properties, aiding in the management of *Ashmari*.
- Its **diuretic effect** enhances urine output, dilutes urinary salts, and prevents crystal aggregation.
- Its **antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory** actions prevent urinary tract infections (UTIs), which are common precipitating factors in stone formation.

CONCLUSION

- The present study was conducted on 40 patients diagnosed with *Mutrashmari* (Urolithiasis), who were randomly divided into two groups. Patients of Group A were treated with *Ikshu Paneeya Kshara*, and patients of Group B were treated with *Mulaka Paneeya Kshara*.
- *Anupana:* *Pashanabhedadi Kwatha Churna Kashaya* – 20 ml, twice daily for both groups.
- Appropriate *Pathya* and *Apathya* were advised to all patients.
- Duration: 28 days.

The effects of treatment in both groups showed statistically highly significant results ($p < 0.001$) in all subjective assessment parameters. The effects of treatment between the groups were statistically non-significant. The reduction in the size of the stone in Group A was significant, whereas in Group B it was highly significant. However, the difference in stone size

reduction between the groups was statistically non-significant.

- The percentage of improvement in Group A on pain abdomen is 86.49%, on Frequency of micturition is 78.05%, on Burning micturition is 40%, on Haematuria is 100%, on size of stone is 61.36% and on descent of stone is 55%.
- The percentage of improvement in Group B on Pain abdomen is 89.74%, on Frequency of micturition is 88.24%, on Burning micturition is 65%, on Haematuria is 100% and on size of stone is 70.73% and on descent of stone is 75%.
- The overall results of treatment in Group A were **55.80%**, and in Group B, **69.21%**. Based on the observations and results, the following hypothesis is accepted:

***Mulaka Paneeya Kshara* is more efficacious than *Ikshu Paneeya Kshara* in the management of *Mutrashmari* (Urolithiasis).**

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